

BRILLO: Investigating the Complex Role of a Robot in the Service Industry

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Abstract—Robots are being deployed in the food and beverage industries to increase the retail of customers. However, robot’s deployment in such scenarios is not a simple task due to the complexity of the interactions and the robots’ limitations, in terms of perceptual capabilities and social intelligence. In particular, the bartending domain represents a challenging scenario that allows robotics to explore approaches both for service-related tasks, such as manipulation of objects for the drinks’ preparations, and social-related tasks, such as engaging interactions for fostering customers’ loyalty. In this work, we present a bartender robot that is able to complete the task of serving drinks while adapting its multi-modal behaviours to customers’ needs.

I. INTRODUCTION

Human bartenders are generally considered service gatekeepers by providing mental support to their customers. Indeed, they are considered a valid alternative to professional counsellors with whom customers often share their problems and information [1]. Human bartenders, therefore, do not only provide a service, but they ensure customer retention by creating a long-lasting relationship. Following such a scenario, the project BRILLO (Bartending Robot for Interactive Long-Lasting Operations) aims to deploy a robot that is able to model its behaviours in rich and multi-modal interactions in real commercial activities [2]. The development of the BRILLO bartender robot includes natural communications modes (verbal and non-verbal), recommendations and personalized interactions for ensuring the users’ engagement with the robot. The BRILLO system possesses cognitive and affective components to adapt its behaviours to model interactions according to the users’ needs, in terms of personalities, expectations, preferences, etc. Moreover, social recovery strategies are considered to account for interaction failures [3]. In this work, we give a brief overview of the BRILLO system, the developed framework and functionalities for interacting with multiple users and meeting their preferences, emotions, and differences.

II. THE BRILLO SYSTEM

In our scenario, we envisioned a system composed of a bartender robot and two graphical interfaces (totem kiosk and tablet) which will be used for registering the user’s information and managing the orders. The bartender robot is in charge

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of preparing and serving the drinks at the counter while interacting with the customers.

A. The Architecture

The cognitive architecture of the robot is composed of multiple layers, and it has been inspired by the BDI (Belief-Desire-Intention) model [4] for modelling both reactivity and proactivity in the robot behaviours, interaction with multi-users by means of multiple instantiated intentions, while modelling long-term knowledge as well as situational assessment through beliefs update mechanisms. The architecture has been developed as ROS nodes, actions, and services that communicate via topics and ad-hoc messages. The architecture, is composed of: 1) a Percepts layer that handles the users’ detection, facial biometric recognition, and the presence of a group of users; 2) a Context-awareness layer that builds the agents and situational awareness based on the information related to the users’ orders, preferences, social engagement with their group and the robot, and emotions; and 3) an Execution layer that according to the built BDIs plans the robot’s actions (both for preparing drinks and interacting with the users).

B. The Bartender Robot

The bartender robot has two Kuka¹ LBR iiwa 14 R820 robotic arms (each of 7 DoF and gripper), attached to a fixed-torso, and a Furhat Robotics head² (called Furhat, 3 DoF). The Furhat robot can have different human facial features, such as representing different ages, genders, ethnicities. We chose the most appropriate face for the bartender role (i.e., neutral) by investigating the effects of gender likeness and agency on people’s perception of the robot.

III. THE BARTENDING SERVICE

The multi-modal and multi-user interactions expected to be supported by the BRILLO system are supported by the use of long-term memory (implemented as a MySQL Database) and semantic memory (implemented as a graph-based memory Neo4J). These two memories are used by the system to recommend and personalise both drinks and interaction modalities according to the interacting user’ persona, needs and preferences.

¹Kuka robotics <https://www.kuka.com>

²Furhat Robotics <https://furhatrobotics.com>

A. Personalisation and Recommendation of the Drinks

The main structure of the semantic database is composed of the flavours of the drinks, the users' preferred drinks and purchases, and the connections between each user and object in the database. Such a structure allows us to use three different strategies for the recommendations of the drinks to the users: 1) the most ordered drinks, 2) the drinks with similar ingredients to the ones already ordered or listed as preferred by the user, and 3) the drinks ordered by other users that have similar ingredients.

B. Personalisation and Recommendation of the Interaction

The BRILLO system uses a variety of information acquired by sensors (e.g., microphones and cameras), previous interactions with the customers, observing and analysing users' behaviours and poses to personalise the interaction with the customers according to their needs and preferences.

The robot's behaviours are modelled for dialogues, the movements of the head and arms, its expression of emotions by two state machines (i.e., one for the Furhat head, one for the interaction) according to the state of the robot bartending service (from the welcoming of the user to the ordering of a drink, to the farewell).

The BRILLO system selects the modalities of the interactions with a user (i.e., gestures, facial expressions, dialogues, and frequency of the interaction) according to the detected level of engagement with the robot. Such recommendation of the interaction relies on a probabilistic estimation of the usefulness of social interactions according to the users' communication modes.

1) *User Detection and Recognition*: Customers are registered at their first visit to the service point, and then they are recognised via biometrical recognition of their faces. The identity of the customers is used to set the energy, frequency and duration of the dialogues, to pick topics of interest for the users, to assign a style of robot behaviours according to the user's preference (i.e., mimicking or friendly behaviours [5]), to manage the priority queue and keep customers engaged while waiting to be served. In particular, customers are categorised according to their personas (i.e., workers on a break, group of friends, families), and their personalities (e.g., extroverted vs. introverted). For example, some customers might be in a hurry and do not prefer to be engaged in small talks with the robots, while others might want to relax and discuss the latest news savouring their preferred drink.

2) *Sentiment and mood analysis*: People's perception of social intelligence in robots can be enhanced by developing a robot that is able to understand and express appropriate emotions that can positively affect the interactions [6]. The BRILLO system uses different tools (e.g., Affectiva, MyVoice-Analysis, Azure Cognitive Services Text Analytics) to recognise users' moods and emotions through sentiment analysis, voice and body posture. According to the users' internal status, the robot is able to express friendly or mimicking emotions. We used two libraries based on Ekman's main emotions with three levels of intensity (high, average, low)

to generate facial emotions for Furhat head, vocal emotions by varying the volume, pitch and speed of the speech.

3) *User Engagement*: The BRILLO system is also able to detect customers' engagement with the robot by identifying groups of people and observing their positions and poses. The bartender robot observes users' pose through a skeleton-based approach detected by the OpenPose library, identifies groups by classifying their position according to the F-formation approach, and uses a Multilayer Perceptron architecture based on the group and pose information to evaluate the level of user's engagement with the robot.

4) *Sarcasm and irony*: The users' information detected through the emotion and sentiment analysis, pose and engagement, are also used by the robot to solve the impossibility of identifying the users' intentions with high accuracy. It can happen, indeed, that the robot is not able to interpret customers' verbal and non-verbal behaviours during their interaction. In this scenario, the robot adopts a coherent or incoherent behaviour, through gestures and speech, generating hilarity in the users, and, consequently, allowing the users to positively perceive the robot and enhancing the success of the interaction [7].

IV. CONCLUSIONS & FUTURE WORKS

A first prototype of the robot that addresses the need for the efficient execution of the multiple service tasks of a bartending scenario (i.e., preparing and serving drinks) has been developed and it is currently in testing within a controlled environment. Future works will include the deployment of the BRILLO system in a real-life scenario to further investigate how to use customers' info to persuade them to purchase goods while observing any concerns about their privacy.

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